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Abstract: Connectives or connective words are words or phrases that link sentences or clauses together. Connectives can be conjunctions, prepositions, or adverbs and are used frequently both in spoken and written English. Connectives are functional words that help a writer link their words together. They serve as the glue of the sentence as they help words to flow and lead on from one to another without sounding awkward or unclear. Without connectives, a written sentence or spoken sentence wouldn't make very much sense. Using connectives strengthens writing skills.

Key words: Connectors, literary speech, academic language, sentence level, suffix.

This chapter investigates the interface between syntax and information structure by concentrating on issues of processing information and constructing a text, drawing on chiefly sixteenth- and seventeenth-century data representing the single genre of letters. The main focus of interest is the perceived differences between grammars of writing prose in the evolution of prose genres. One type of difference can be depicted by polarizing a prose grammar that uses coordinator-like connectives such as and, but, and for as structuring devices at the levels of discourse and text and one that exploits semantically explicit, syntactically hierarchizing subordinators at the clause and sentence level, frequently also making use of either semantically explicit or looser adverbial connectors, the latter called "transitional," at the levels of text and discourse. Besides providing a quantitative analysis, the chapter aims to illustrate that not only the role of genre but also that of the evolving grammars and registers of writing (conventionalized variably depending on the varying levels of linguistic and stylistic literacy of the writers) should be carefully considered in assessing what implications information-structural properties have upon syntactic variation and change.

Gardener and his forms. Conjunctions, like auxiliaries, are syntactic means of communication, and are distinguished from them by the fact that, in addition to expressing a subordinate relationship, they also form an equal relationship. Conjunctions indicate different connections and grammatical relations between parts of a sentence, parts of a compound sentence equal to a simple sentence. The essence of connectors, types of connectors in the Uzbek literary language, words related to these types have been widely studied in our linguistics. In the existing literature, there are different points of view on the types of connectors and which words belong to these

types, that is, a unit designated as a connector in one case is included in the list of predicates in another case, a unit designated as an auxiliary is recognized as a connector. Conjunctions are clear the reason for not being identified is probably that they have not been studied linguistically.

The connective to be - a homonym (according to another point of view, a lexical-semantic variant, that is, one of the meanings) of an existential verb - is unique not only in the sense that it is completely grammaticalized and participates in the formation of analytical forms, but also in a paradigmatic sense: which, in the course of the evolution of the morphological system, has lost its change in presentation by persons and numbers.

Conjunctions should also be divided into three groups (pure conjunctions, relative conjunctions, adverbial conjunctions). The group of pure conjunctions is characterized by auxiliary words such as and, and, or, or, or, but, but, but, because, for shutting, if, ie, which are used only as a conjunction. The group of adverbial conjunctions includes -ki (-kirm) and -u (-yu), -da, -mi, which can act both as a conjunction and as a burden. It is noted in many sources that -u (-yu) fully fulfills the linking function of suffixes, and that suffix -mi also has binding properties. It will be wet, Kareem has come, and the riot will start. The suffix -mi, used in these sentences, performs the function of linking simple sentences together, expressing the meaning of emphasis. Relative conjunctions include such words as sometimes, one, at the time, still sometimes, (sometimes) that have an "intermediate third" nature (both independent and auxiliary) that have grown from independent word groups. An example is the repeated form. For example, 1. Sometimes he spent the night in Karatoy's office, sometimes in a tea house. 2. The rain, which has been pouring for two days, has frozen everything. 3. Sometimes it snows, sometimes it rains. The functions of the words sometimes, sometimes (sometimes), while used in these sentences are very close to the conjunctions.

Words that come after nouns, pronouns, verbs, and adjectives and make them grammatically dependent on another word (usually a verb) are called auxiliaries. Auxiliaries combine with the preceding independent words in a sentence and add meanings such as means, purpose, cause, time, space, and together with these words, act as a single sentence.

According to the origin of assistants: pure assistants and auxiliary assistants:

1) pure auxiliaries include words that have completely lost their dictionary meaning: with, for, like, like, over, while, until;

2) auxiliary words include words such as towards, other, because of, through, due to, despite, after, out of, since, according to, while, because of.

The group of words used in the role of auxiliaries is formed as a result of the use of independent words in speech as auxiliaries, i.e. grammaticalization: a) noun auxiliaries also have an independent meaning in speech, also used as an auxiliary noun, is composed of the following words belonging to the adjective or adverbial group: side, outside, height etc.; from adjectives such as because of, because of, through, against, while, around, according to, different, other; the nose is made up of before, after, since, mainly, according to, after; b) verb auxiliaries arise as a result of the use of one of the verbs in adjective or adverbial forms as an auxiliary in speech. They consist of words such as: see, fit, look, start, order, see, turn, say.

Language development further progresses after preschool age, with learners expanding their proficiencies in vocabulary, grammar, and discourse through adolescence and potentially through their entire life as they move through a range of social contexts. Connectives (e.g., despite, therefore) are cohesive devices that explicitly indicate how clauses or sentences are to be meaningfully linked. In particular, the knowledge of connectives is associated with text comprehension, whereas the productive use of connectives is related to more complex argumentation in academic texts. Previous studies suggest that the knowledge of connectives develops gradually and is not complete when children enter schools. It is especially relevant to academic language proficiency defines being academically proficient as “knowing and being able to use general and content-specific vocabulary, specialized or complex grammatical structures, and multifarious language functions and discourse structures – all for the purpose of acquiring new knowledge and skills, interacting about a topic, or imparting information to others.”

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